

ORIGINAL ARTICLE**A Study of Situational Leadership Style at PT Singosari, Tidung, Rappocini, Makassar City, South Sulawesi, Indonesia.****Jamaluddin¹ | Muliana² | Haedar Akib³ | Rudi Salam⁴ | Maya Kasmita⁵ | A. Oktamaya Tenri⁶**^{1,2,3,4,5} Universitas Negeri Makassar, Makassar, South Sulawesi, Indonesia.²Email: Muliana0206@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Organizational success in achieving goals and objectives depends on the manager and his leadership style. This study aims to describe the effectiveness of the application of the situational leadership style at PT Singosari Timur Jaya Makassar. To achieve this goal, the researcher determined 5 (five) informants with the type of research and the approach used was descriptive qualitative. Collecting data through interview techniques, observation, and documentation. The results showed that the warehouse head of PT Singosari Timur Jaya Makassar was classified as having implemented situational leadership well, with the involvement of the leader in determining and assigning tasks to employees that had been running optimally, implementing relationship behavior with employees well, and the attitude of the leadership in addressing the readiness of followers effectively viewed from the indicators of telling style, selling style, participating style, and delegating style.

Keywords: *Leadership, Situational Leadership, Leadership Style.*

INTRODUCTION

Leadership is the backbone of organizational development (Boukis, Koritos, Daunt, & Papastathopoulos, 2020; Özer & Tinaztepe, 2014; Xie et al., 2018). Organizations are simply disorganized assemblages of people and machines without leadership. Leadership also means the ability to influence (Davila & Elvira, 2012; Kanat-Maymon, Elimelech, & Roth, 2020; Niswaty, Juniati, Darwis, Salam, & Arhas, 2019). Without good leadership, a leader will not be able to achieve the vision, mission, and goals set by the organization and develop strategies with his power to influence his subordinates in accordance with organizational goals. Leaders are those whose presence is expected

and whose voice is heard by followers (Ali, Jangga, Ismail, Kamal, & Ali, 2015; Sudaryono, 2014).

A leader can do various ways of influencing and motivating subordinates or other people to take actions that are always directed towards achieving organizational goals (Ncha 2011; Bubu & Offiong 2014). This method reflects the leader's attitudes and views of the people they lead and is a reflection of the leadership style. The success of an organization in achieving its goals and objectives depends on the manager and his leadership style. Leadership style is a leadership model where the leader can influence a group for the sake of achieving goals (Çetin, Karabay, & Efe, 2012; Gameda & Lee, 2020; Pihie, Sadeghi, & Elias, 2011). This study focuses more on the situational leadership style that has been developed by Hersey and Blanchard, which emphasizes the relationship between effective leadership styles and the maturity level of their followers.

The key to leadership effectiveness is contingency theory, namely choosing the correct style of a leader based on the interaction of internal and external factors with the organization (Awaru, 2015; Handayani, 2020; Irawati, 2020; Ishak, Niswaty, & Guntur 2020). The situational or contingency approach is a theory that seeks to find a middle ground between the view that says there are universal principles of organization and management, and the view that argues that each organization is unique and has different situations so that it must be faced with a certain leadership style. Leaders must be able to accurately assess the readiness of their followers and use a leadership style that is appropriate for that level of readiness (Irek & Charles 2012: Asrar-ul-Haq & Kuchinke, 2016)

Leadership is an important factor in increasing the morale of employees in companies such as companies engaged in the distribution of drinking water. A company that is engaged in the distribution of drinking water is a company that provides and provides services by delivering bottled drinking water "Cleo" for the public to enjoy.

According to Siagian, (2003), leadership is a person's ability to influence others (his subordinates) in such a way that the other person is willing to do the will of the leader even though personally it may not be liked by him. Leadership is the process of influencing and supporting others to work together enthusiastically to achieve goals (Irek 2012; Kartono, 2011; Thoha, 2014; Enor & Chime 2015)

The situational leadership style is quite interesting in the current era of globalization, because leaders with this style will always try to adapt to the situation and conditions of the organization, and are flexible in adapting/adjusting to the maturity of subordinates and their work environment (Enor & Ebaye 2011). This is following the current conditions and situations which require leaders to be accommodating and aspirational towards their work environment.

Based on the results of preliminary observations made by researchers at PT Singosari Timur Jaya Makassar, the phenomenon encountered by researchers is that the leadership used so far is only limited to relationships and trust in leaders and employees for the abilities of their employees. The warehouse head of PT Singosari Timur Jaya also

sees the experience as a reference for the ability of his employees and in giving different treatment to his employees.

This study will focus on the situational leadership style of the warehouse chief at PT. Singosari Timur Jaya. Given that in the world of work, a leader in managing subordinates is often influenced by circumstances or situations that occur, depending on the situation that is being lived.

METHOD

The variable in this study is a single variable, namely the situational leadership style at PT Singosari Timur Jaya Makassar. This research uses a qualitative approach. The qualitative research method is a research method based on the post-positivism philosophy, used to examine the condition of a natural object, (as opposed to an experiment) where the researcher is the key instrument, the sampling of data sources is done purposively and snowball, the collection technique is by triangulation. (combined), the data analysis is inductive/qualitative, and the results of qualitative research emphasize meaning rather than generalization (Sugiyono, 2018).

The type of research used is descriptive research. Descriptive research is a study conducted with the main objective of providing an objective description or description of a situation. This type of descriptive research was chosen in this study because it is suitable for use in researching the application of the situational leadership style at PT Singosari Timur Jaya Makassar. An activity that is quite important in the entire research process is data reduction. With data reduction, it can be seen about the meaning of the data that has been collected so that the research results will be immediately known.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of research through interviews, observation, and documentation, it is known that the situational leadership style at PT Singosasi Timur Jaya Makassar can be analyzed based on the theory described in the previous chapter. The data presented in this study are data obtained from interviews with 5 informants.

Therefore, the following will discuss the situational leadership style following what took place at PT Singosari Timur Jaya Makassar.

Telling Style

In this style, the leader tells subordinates what to do, where, and how to do it. Also, the leader determines the structure or role of the subordinates. Based on the interviews conducted with the head of the warehouse, please note that the head of the warehouse provides clear directions such as how to do it, what are the targets or goals that must be achieved, and steps or procedures that must be taken so that the results obtained can be maximized. Do not forget to keep the monitor running so you can control them so that the task is always directed.

The warehouse head also emphasized the importance of control in dealing with employees who are unable and unwilling or unsure so that they can always see the progress of what they are doing, to what extent have been done, and also so that it can be seen whether the instructions given are clear or not, because clarity very affects the results of the assignment given or the task is completed sooner or later.

According to the interview with the helper (Nasaruddin, 2020), It was found that the head of the warehouse in giving the task always explained the task in advance. Leaders always give tasks directly to their subordinates. The warehouse head provides directions to the targets given to subordinates following the abilities of the subordinates. The warehouse head emphasizes more on work supervision based on the results of written data reports on the work performance of his subordinates. The warehouse head continues to carry out superficial surveillance to ensure employees are working well but emphasizes more on the reports given to him each week.

From the observations, it was found that this style was most appropriate for low follower readiness (R1). It emphasizes high task behavior and limited relationship behavior. This leadership style is characteristic of a one-way communication style. The leader tells the individual or group what, how, why, when, and where a job is done. The leader always provides clear instructions, detailed directions, and supervises the work in person.

Selling style (seller)

In this style, the leader provides direction through two-way communication and gives directed tasks. This style arises when the readiness of followers to do work increases so that leaders need to continue to provide a guiding attitude because workers are not ready to take full responsibility for the job.

The head of the warehouse emphasizes the importance of briefing or explaining the direction of the task clearly and specifically so that subordinates are more motivated to complete the task properly and feel cared for by the leadership. Employees who have the desire to carry out their duties even though their abilities are lacking or cannot at all be directed and given confidence. It remains us who have to be clever in communicating and directing them.

According to interviews with drivers, the warehouse head always allowed his employees to have an opinion. The leader always accepts suggestions and opinions from subordinates. And decision making usually always considers the opinions of employees. But usually with a more detailed explanation, the leader's decision can be influenced by his subordinates.

From the observations, it was found that this style was most appropriate for moderate employee readiness (R2). It emphasizes on a high number of tasks and relationship behavior. At this stage of the leadership style, a leader still provides direction, but he uses two-way communication and provides emotional support to individuals to motivate

employee self-confidence. This style arises when the competence of an individual or group increases so that the leader needs to continue to provide a guiding attitude because the individual or group is not ready to take full responsibility for the process at work.

Participating style

This style encourages workers and leaders to be proud of each other and simultaneously facilitates the work of subordinates with enthusiasm. This style emphasizes leaders who are willing to help employees, based on the results of interviews with the head of the warehouse (Mahmud, 2020), on several occasions, the warehouse head has also helped employees in the work process. The warehouse head sometimes participates in the work of employees by contributing ideas and ideas so that they are more motivated to complete work. Because sometimes some employees feel pessimistic about not achieving their monthly targets. Here is my role as a good listener and ready to help.

The warehouse head's statement was confirmed by an interview answer from the admin (Susan, 2020), leaders always free employees in completing tasks in their way, but leaders can always be used as a place to ask for suggestions and opinions.

Based on the observations it was found that this style was appropriate for the readiness of high followers with moderate motivation (R3). It emphasizes a high number of relationship behaviors but a low number of task behaviors. The leadership style at this stage encourages individuals or groups to share ideas and at the same time facilitate work with the enthusiasm they show. This style arises when employees feel confident in doing their job so that the warehouse head is no longer too direct. The warehouse head maintains open communication but now does so in a tendency to be more of a good listener and ready to help his followers.

Delegating style (delegate)

This style is effective because followers are considered competent and fully motivated to take responsibility for their work. Employees who are given a delegating style are considered pro and have experience and expertise. Usually, I often exchange ideas and even ask their opinion. In carrying out their duties, they always provide progress, and whatever the obstacles are. The warehouse head also explained that employees who are given this style can best use resources that encourage the achievement of goals in carrying out tasks.

Based on the results of interviews with drivers (Safar, 2020), leaders usually give responsibility to employees who have worked for a long time. Employees, including senior employees, are often given direct duties and responsibilities such as delivering large quantities of gallons to regular customers.

Based on observations, this style is considered the most appropriate for the readiness of high followers (R4). This emphasizes both sides, namely the high work behavior and relationship behavior where the leadership style at this stage tends to shift responsibility for the decision-making process and its implementation. This style is effective because

followers are considered competent and fully motivated to take responsibility for their work. The task of a leader is only to monitor the progress of the work.

DISCUSSION

Telling Style

Findings in the field through observations and interviews conducted by the author with the head of the warehouse and several employees regarding the notification style applied to employees emphasize the importance of clear directions or instructions and maximum control. But before that, the head of the warehouse emphasized the importance of knowing the true extent of the employees' abilities. This is in line with the theory that this style required clear and specific instructions and strict control or supervision. From the observations made, the telling style is applied to employees who are considered to be at the readiness level of R1 (low).

Selling style

Findings in the field through observations and interviews conducted by the author with the head of the warehouse and several employees regarding the selling style, it is known that the warehouse head emphasizes the importance of directing or explaining the direction of the task clearly and specifically so that subordinates are more motivated to complete tasks properly and feel cared for by the leadership. This is in line with the theory that leaders need to start showing supportive behavior to provoke self-confidence while maintaining their enthusiasm. Observations made found that the selling style (seller) is applied to employees who are considered to have a readiness level of R2 who are considered or feel unable but willing to do work.

Participating Style

Findings in the field through observations and interviews conducted by the author with the head of the warehouse and several employees regarding the participating style, it is known that on several occasions the warehouse head also helps employees in the work process. This is in line with the theoretical basis that leaders are no longer too direct. Leaders maintain open communication, by tending to be good listeners and ready to help their followers. From the observations, it was found that the participating force was applied to employees who were considered to be at the R3 (moderate) readiness level.

Delegating style

Findings in the field through observations and interviews conducted by the author with the head of the warehouse and several employees regarding the delegating style, it is known that employees who are given the delegating style are considered to be pro and have experience and expertise. This is in line with the theoretical basis that in this style leaders tend to shift responsibility for the decision-making process and its implementation. From the observations made it was found that the delegating style was applied to

employees with a readiness level of R4 (high), considered capable and confident in doing work.

The form of high task behavior can be seen in the warehouse head's statement which reveals that he sets targets for his subordinates, including the deadline for completing these targets. The Warehouse Head always provides directions for assigned tasks and supervises the work of his subordinates in the form of daily work reports. Also, the Warehouse Head has a relationship orientation which can be seen in his efforts to provide support to his subordinates whenever they face work problems. Even the Head of the Warehouse is not ashamed to invite his subordinates to discuss and provide opinions in discussing the problems that occur. The warehouse head welcomes and responds to complaints from his subordinates well and is easy to contact when his subordinates want to communicate with him. The Warehouse Head does not hesitate to give praise and acknowledge the performance of his subordinates every time there is an achievement made by his subordinates. Knowing the information from the above interview, the researcher concluded that the Warehouse Head was too dominant in the S2 (selling) leadership style where based on the level of readiness of his subordinates, the leadership style that was more widely applied by the Warehouse Head was S4 (delegating) leadership style. The warehouse head has a high leadership style in selling leadership style. The selling leadership style has high task behavior and relationship behavior to subordinates. In the selling leadership style, the leader still directs the achievement of targets but also explains why provides suggestions and encourages involvement in decision making. The application of the S2 (selling) leadership style for the readiness level of subordinates at R4 (very high) shows that the situational leadership is less effective so that the subordinates cannot develop optimally because the leader has more discussions with subordinates, rather than giving them the confidence to solve these problems independently. S2 leadership style (selling) is shown to subordinates who still need direction and input because they are still relatively inexperienced, in contrast to the two subordinates of the Warehouse Head who have a very high level of readiness.

CONCLUSION

Based on the formulation of the problem and the results of the research conducted by the author on Situational Leadership Style at PT Singosari Timur Jaya Makassar, it is concluded that the leadership behavior of the warehouse chief at PT Singosari Timur Jaya Makassar includes consultative style (selling), delegative style (delegating), participatory style (participating) and instructive style (telling). In a consultative style (selling), the leader provides direction through two-way communication and gives directed tasks. The delegative style (delegating) is evidenced by the warehouse head's instructions to the subordinates with a little direction because here the subordinates have been able to independently carry out the assigned task. The participatory style (participating) is indicated by the leader who is always open to receiving ideas, ideas, and suggestions from under him which will then be considered in decision making. The last style, namely the

instructive style (telling) is proven by providing strict supervision by giving leaders to subordinates who are unable and unwilling to carry out the task.

REFERENCES

- Ali, N. M., Jangga, R., Ismail, M., Kamal, S. N.-I. M., & Ali, M. N. (2015). Influence of Leadership Styles in Creating Quality Work Culture. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 31, 161–169. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(15\)01143-0](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(15)01143-0)
- Asrar-ul-Haq, M., & Kuchinke, K. P. (2016). Impact of leadership styles on employees' attitude towards their leader and performance: Empirical evidence from Pakistani banks. *Future Business Journal*, 2(1), 54–64. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbj.2016.05.002>
- Awaru, O. T. (2015). Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan Transaksional Dan Transformasional Terhadap Kinerja Guru Sma Di Kabupaten Sinjai. *Jurnal Ad'ministrare*, 2(1), 27–35.
- Boukis, A., Koritos, C., Daunt, K. L., & Papastathopoulos, A. (2020). Effects of customer incivility on frontline employees and the moderating role of supervisor leadership style. *Tourism Management*, 77, 103997. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2019.103997>
- Bubu, D. N. G., & Offiong, I. (2014). An analysis of a new dimension of personal names and documentation in Ibibio folk philosophy: An exercise in linguistic philosophy. *Journal Of Integrative Humanism Ghana*, 3(2).
- Ncha, G. B. (2011). Existential Justice: Integrative and Humanistic Perspectives. *Journal Of Integrative Humanism Ghana*, 1.
- Çetin, M., Karabay, M. E., & Efe, M. N. (2012). The Effects of Leadership Styles and the Communication Competency of Bank Managers on the Employee's Job Satisfaction: The Case of Turkish Banks. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 58, 227–235. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.09.996>
- Davila, A., & Elvira, M. M. (2012). Humanistic leadership: Lessons from Latin America. *Journal of World Business*, 47(4), 548–554. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwb.2012.01.008>
- Enor, F. N., & Chime, J. (2015). Reflections on revolution in theory and practice. *Pyrex Journal of History and Culture*, 1(2), 13-16.
- Enor, F., & Ebaye, S. E. (2011). Military Coups as a Negation of Social Revolutions: the Nigerian Experience. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(3), 372-372.
- Gemeda, H. K., & Lee, J. (2020). Leadership styles, work engagement and outcomes among information and communications technology professionals: A cross-national study. *Heliyon*, 6(4), e03699. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e03699>
- Handayani, R. (2020). The Effect of Leadership Style and Work Discipline on Employee

- Performance at PT Indonesia Nippon Seiki Cikande Serang. *PINISI Discretion Review*, 3(1), 53–60.
- Irawati, L. (2020). The Influence of Leadership and Motivation on Employee Performance at the South Tangerang Fire and Rescue Service. *Jurnal Ad'ministrare*, 7(1), 119–128.
- Irek, N. E. (2016). Music as a Tool for Communicating Good Governance in Nigeria: A Periscopic Survey of Selected Nigerian Musicians. *West African Association for Commonwealth Literature and Languages Studies Journal*, 4(1), 1-20.
- Irek, N. E., & Charles, E. (2012). Developing the Arts Industry through the Theatre Profession.
- Ishak, M., Niswaty, R., & Guntur, M. (2020). Competitiveness of Public Services, Non-Formal Education Institutions Center of Education Indonesia. *GNOSI: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Human Theory and Praxis*, 3(1), 53-60.
- Kanat-Maymon, Y., Elimelech, M., & Roth, G. (2020). Work motivations as antecedents and outcomes of leadership: Integrating self-determination theory and the full range leadership theory. *European Management Journal*.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emj.2020.01.003>
- Kartono, K. (2011). *Pemimpin dan Kepemimpinan*. Jakarta: Rajawali Grafindo Perkasa.
- Mahmud. (2020). *wawancara langsung*.
- Nasaruddin. (2020). *wawancara langsung*.
- Niswaty, R., Juniati, F., Darwis, M., Salam, R., & Arhas, S. H. (2019). The Effectiveness of Leadership Functions Implementation in The Makassar Departement of Manpower. *JPBM (Jurnal Pendidikan Bisnis dan Manajemen)*, 5(1), 1–10.
- Özer, F., & Tınaztepe, C. (2014). Effect of Strategic Leadership Styles on Firm Performance: A Study in a Turkish SME. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 150, 778–784. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.09.059>
- Pihie, Z. A. L., Sadeghi, A., & Elias, H. (2011). Analysis of Head of Departments Leadership Styles: Implication for Improving Research University Management Practices. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 29, 1081–1090. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.11.341>
- Safar. (2020). *wawancara langsung*.
- Siagian, S. P. (2003). *Teori dan Praktek Kepemimpinan*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Sudaryono. (2014). *Leaderships: Teori dan Praktek Kepemimpinan*. Jakarta: Lentera Ilmu Cendekia.
- Sugiyono. (2018). *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Susan. (2020). *wawancara langsung*.
- Thoha, M. (2014). *Kepemimpinan dalam Manajemen*. Jakarta: PT RajaGrafindo Persada.
- Xie, Y., Xue, W., Li, L., Wang, A., Chen, Y., Zheng, Q., ... Li, X. (2018). Leadership style and innovation atmosphere in enterprises: An empirical study. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 135, 257–265. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2018.05.017>